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APPENDIX 1. DISCUSSION OF THE SOURCES

Religious activities on Ox Heart Hill before the tenth century are primarily documented in a narrative credited to Du Guangting. This account is said to be part of *Records of Evidential Miracles in Support of Daoism* (*Daojiao lingyan ji* 道教靈驗記, hereafter *DLJ*), compiled by Du in the early tenth century. However, the intricate history of the text’s transmission raises questions that warrant further discussion.

The *DLJ* has survived in two editions. The primary edition, comprising fifteen *juan*, is included in the Daoist Canon of the Ming dynasty (*Zhengtong Daozang* 正統道藏, hereafter *DZ*) published in 1445. The second edition is an abridged version, comprising six *juan* and found in the extensive Daoist anthology *Cloudy Bookcase with Seven Labels* (*Yunji qiqian* 雲笈七籤, hereafter *YQ*). Compiled by Zhang Junfang 張君房 (fl. 1008–1025), the *YQ* itself has also been preserved in the Ming Daoist Canon. The overlaps between these two editions, which I will hereafter refer to as the *DZ* and *YQ* editions respectively, are significant but not complete. The *YQ* edition contains 125 miracle tales,¹ of which eighty-eight are also found in the *YQ* edition (and arranged in exactly the same order)² and thirty-seven are not. Of these thirty-seven, one

¹ I count all “appended” (*fu* 附) tales as separate entries. I have not included in my counting the two prefaces by Emperor Zhenzong (one mistakenly ascribed to Huizong), the original preface by Du Guangting, and the last entry in the *DZ* edition (i.e., “Account of the Evidential Miracle of the Book of the Heavenly Lads, [Spoken] by the Most High” 太上天童經靈驗錄). Given that this last entry is at variance with all the other entries in its title and arrangement (namely, it is called “so-and-so *lingyan lu*” 靈驗錄, instead of simply “so-and-so *yan*” 驗, and it is placed after Zhenzong’s preface in the text), it is likely not part of Du’s original text.

² In three of these eighty-eight entries, there are discrepancies in wording between the two versions in three instances. Among them, two entries in the *YQ* version, found in *juan* 119 and 121 respectively, are excerpts rather than full transcripts. In a third entry, there are slight differences in content (i.e., “Evidence of Liu Zaizhi reciting the Tianpeng spell” 劉載之誦天蓬咒驗 in *juan* 119 of the *YQ* edition). For a meticulous comparison between entries in the two editions, see Miyazawa Masayori, “‘Dōkyō reigenki’ ni tsuite.” Miyazawa, however, missed three identical

tells of a story about Li Longqian and Ox Heart Hill. Entitled “Evidence from Li Shang Felling Pines and Cypresses in the Ancient Abbey on Ox Heart Hill in Longzhou” (李賞斫龍州牛心山古觀松栢驗), this tale provides a major source material for my discussion in this paper. That this tale was absent in the *DZ* edition raises the question of whether it was truly part of Du’s original work, but evidence suggests that most likely it was.

First, consider the motivations that drove Zhang to compile the *YQ* and the way he compiled it. After receiving the *jinshi* degree in 1005, Zhang served in several low and middle-ranking offices. In 1013, he was tasked with compiling the Song-dynasty Daoist Canon (which he called the *Da Song tiangong baozang* 大宋天宮寶藏). This massive compilation, comprising 4,565 *juan*, was completed and presented to the throne in 1019. Zhang’s *YQ* was finished thirteen years later and originally comprised 120 *juan*. As Zhang himself stated in the preface, the *YQ* was intended as a condensed version of the vast Song Daoist Canon.³ The significant overlap between the *DZ* and the *YQ* editions of the *DLJ* lends to credibility to this claim.

Then why are thirty-seven tales in the *YQ* edition missing from the *DZ* edition? The most probable explanation is that the original text of the *DLJ*, which Zhang worked with in the early eleventh century, has not survived in its entirety and that the *DZ* edition we have today is merely a portion of the original. This is also the view of most other scholars, including Franciscus Verellen, who argues that the *YQ* “substantially complements the present text [of the *DZ* edition of the *DLJ*]. With thirty-six additional stories, it allows the reconstitution of 22 percent of the original (in terms of titles), against the 25 percent (in terms of *juan*) missing in the present edition [of the *DLJ*].”⁴

That the present *DZ* edition of the *DLJ* does not include the entirety of its original finds support in Du’s original preface to the text, which states that the *DLJ* comprised twenty *juan*, not fifteen.⁵ Du’s description is corroborated by bibliographies from Song times. All extant bibliographies before the thirteenth century that mention the *DLJ* describe it a work of twenty

entries that are found in both *juan* 121 of the *YQ* edition and *juan* 15 of the *DZ* edition. For correction, see Luo Zhengming, *Du guangting daojiao xiaoshuo yanjiu*, 275.

³ For a brief discussion of Zhang and his *YQ*, see the editor’s “Foreword” 前言 in *YQ*, i–vi.

⁴ Schipper and Verellen, *The Taoist Canon: A Historical Companion to the Daozang*, 419.

⁵ *DLJ*, 154–55.

juan.⁶ The first bibliography that describes the *DLJ* as comprising fifteen *juan* is *Detailed Comments on the Catalogue of the Daoist Canon* (*Daozang mulu xiangzhu* 道藏目錄詳註), compiled by Bo Yunji 白雲霽 in 1626 and what was then preserved in the Ming Daoist Canon.⁷ All this suggests that portions of the original twenty-*juan* edition of the *DLJ* were lost, most likely between the thirteenth and fifteenth centuries. Although the precise timing of and the reasons for this loss cannot be determined, it is tempting to think of the several massive destructions of Daoist texts ordered by the Mongol rulers in the thirteenth century as possible causes.⁸

A careful study of the content and structure of the *DLJ* lends further support to the theory that the thirty-seven tales missing in the present *DZ* edition had been entries in the last few *juan* of the original *DLJ* which were lost between the thirteenth and mid-fifteenth centuries. Modeled on the Buddhist apologetic literature and some earlier Daoist adaptations, the *DLJ* is a collection of tales of miraculous intervention that provide evidence supporting the tenets of the Daoist faith and caution against acts of sacrilege. In the present *DZ* edition, these tales are organized according to several categories of supernatural agents effecting these miracles. These supernatural agents, each explicitly identified in the heading of each *juan*, include Daoist buildings (temples and monasteries), icons (statues and paintings), deities (the deified Laozi, the deified Celestial Master Zhang Daoling, and Perfected Persons, and else), sacred writings (such as scriptures, talismans, and spells), ritual objects (bells, chimes, and liturgical utensils) and practices (the Daoist rituals of Retreat and Offering, as well as liturgical memorials and petitions).⁹

The thirty-seven tales missing in the *DZ* edition are organized according to the same principle. Nineteen of these tales, all of which are in *juan* 120 and 121 of the *YQ* edition, are miracles pertaining to the Daoist ritual practices, that is, the category of supernatural agents featured in the last two *juan* of the present *DZ* edition. The remaining eighteen tales, all in *juan* 122 of the *YQ* edition, report miracles associated with a more varied array of supernatural agents

⁶ For a full survey on these bibliographies, see Miyazawa Masayori, “‘Dōkyō reigenki’ ni tsuite.”

⁷ Miyazawa Masayori, “‘Dōkyō reigenki’ ni tsuite.”

⁸ For a full discussion of the Yuan destruction of Daoist scriptures, see Liu Weiting, “Yuandai fo dao bianzheng tanwei.”

⁹ Verellen, “‘Evidential Miracles in Support of Taoism.’”

that extend beyond the categories listed in the *DZ* edition and thus complement them. These include three cautionary tales against encroachment on monastic land (*changzhu* 常住), two against logging in the vicinity Daoist monasteries, another two discouraging any damage to Daoist buildings, such as theft of door panels and column bases, and finally eleven miracles that demonstrate the power of sacred Daoist geographical landmarks. The settings of these eighteen tales are also noteworthy: twelve of them are set in Sichuan, especially the Chengdu area, and the most frequently mentioned reign titles are those used between 874 and 892. These features align seamlessly with those of the miracles in the *DZ* edition. Many a scholar have argued that the *DLJ* was completed between 905 and 908 during Du Guangting's second visit to Sichuan and that many of the stories in the collection concern Sichuan and the reigns of Tang emperors Yizong (r. 859–873) and Xizong (r. 873–888).¹⁰

The narrative of Ox Heart Hill and Li Longqian, which my paper draws on, is intended to provide the backdrop for a cautionary tale against logging in the vicinity of Daoist monasteries. The tale revolves around Li Shang, a local officer who received divine punishment for cutting down trees on Ox Heart Hill, the location of an ancient Daoist abbey associated with the cult of Li Longqian. The purport and setting of this tale (i.e., in Sichuan and around the late ninth or early tenth century) both conform closely to the general features of the *DLJ*. Additionally, as a cautionary tale about a local officer, the story of Li Shang also aligns with another aspect of the *DLJ* observed by Arao Toshio. Whereas many scholars have focused on Buddho-Daoist tensions manifested in this text,¹¹ Arao contends that in Du Guangting's view, it was the local officials who posed the most substantial threat to Daoist establishments during the turmoil of the late ninth century. This perceived threat motivated Du to compile the *DLJ*, in which around forty percent of the tales relate to acts of sacrilege committed by local officials and only less than ten percent relate to the Buddhist clergy.¹²

All this evidence suggests that the story of Li Shang was part of Du's original version of the *DLJ* but were later lost. Yet what sources did Du rely on for the religious history of Ox Heart

¹⁰ Zhou Xibo, *Daojiao lingyanji kaotan*, 35. For a thorough analysis of the spatial and temporal settings of the tales in the *DLJ*, see Yusa Noboru, “‘Dōkyō reigenki’ kō (ichi)”; “‘Dōkyō reigenki’ kō (ni)”; “‘Dōkyō reigenki’ ni tsuite.”

¹¹ Verellen, “‘Evidential Miracles in Support of Taoism.’” Huang Yong, *Daojiao biji xiaoshuo yanjiu*.

¹² Arao Toshio, “Du Kōtei ‘Dōkyō reigenki’ no ōhōkan ni tsuite”.

Hill prior to his own times? On this question, an entry in Zhu Mu's geographical treatise *An Overview of Scenic Spots in the Realm* (*Fangyu shenglan* 方輿勝覽) provides some clues.¹³ In this short entry on the Shrine to Li Longxian [Longqian], Zhu cited two sources (i.e., the *DLJ* and the "Record of Marvels of Ox Heart Hill" [*Niuxin shan lingyi ji* 牛心山靈異記]) and checked them against the Tang dynastic history. It seems clear that the "Record of Marvels of Ox Heart Hill" refers not to a book, but a stele inscription (*beiji* 碑記) inside Li's shrine. This stele was recorded by Wang Xiangzhi 王象之 (1163–1230) in his *Catalogue of Stele Inscriptions in the Realm* (*Yudi beiji mu* 輿地碑記目), albeit without a transcription of its content:

"Record of Marvels of Ox Heart Hill: Inside the Temple of Manifest Aid on Ox Heart [Hill], also known as the Li Longxian Temple. Name of the author is not recorded in the temple inscription" (牛心山靈異記：在牛心之顯濟廟，即李龍仙廟也。廟碑不載撰人名氏).¹⁴

In addition to this catalog of steles, Wang also completed a geographical treatise titled *Descriptions of Scenic Spots in the Realm* (*Yudi jisheng* 輿地紀勝) in 1227. These two geographical works, by Wang and Zhu respectively, share many similarities, and scholars have debated on their precise relationship. This debate notwithstanding, it is fair to say that Wang's work was, to say the least, an important source that Zhu consulted in writing his own.¹⁵ Therefore, it is perhaps apposite to speculate that Wang had included in his *Yudi jisheng* either a transcription or summary of the stele inside Li's shrine, which Zhu later incorporated into his own work. Unfortunately, this is cannot be confirmed, since the chapter on Longzhou in *Yudi jisheng* are now lost. Given that this stele and Du Guangting's account in the *DLJ* overlap significantly in content, what is their precise relationship? It is certainly possible that the stele was a mere inscription of Du's account, but it is important to note that the miraculous tale of Li Shang felling trees and consequently receiving divine punishment, albeit the focus of Du's narrative, was not at all mentioned in Zhu Mu's summary of the stele inscription. In view of this discrepancy, it seems more likely that the stele had been erected inside the shrine before Du's

¹³ Zhu Mu, *Fangyu shenglan*, 70.1231. For a full translation of this entry, see Appendix 2.3.

¹⁴ Wang Xiangzhi, *Yudi beiji mu*, 4.152.

¹⁵ For a discussion of the relationship between these two geographical treatises, see Moser, "One Land of Many Places."

time (or at least its content had been circulating by then) and that Du incorporated this narrative as contextual information in his account of Li Shang's experiences. Additionally, the title of the stele inscription, foregrounding the marvels of the *hill* instead of the *deity*, also aligns with the religious discourse before Song times, as I have discussed in this paper.

The narrative in the *DLJ* provides the most comprehensive account of religious activities on Ox Heart Hill in Tang times and earlier. Its credibility can be corroborated by two independent sources. The *DLJ* records construction activities on the hill, ordered by the Tang court in 824, but it is brief. It states simply that “in the fourth year of Changqing [824], palace envoys Zhang Shiqian, Wang Yuanyou, and Prefect Yuchi Rui made repairs.” The same event was also recorded in *Jiu Tang shu* and *Zizhi tongjian* (see translations in Appendixes 2.2 and 2.3). Considerable but not complete overlaps between these records¹⁶ indicate that they were based on different sources. The overlap between the *DLJ* and *Jiu Tang shu* is particularly noteworthy. Given that *Jiu Tang shu* was compiled at the Later Jin (936–947) court in a haste of a few years between 941 and 945 and that the *DLJ* was completed sometime between 905 and 908 in Sichuan, the *DLJ* was an unlikely source for the Tang dynastic history. Since the annals (*benji* 本紀) in *Jiu Tang shu* until around 840 are believed to have been based on the Tang veritable records (*shilu* 實錄),¹⁷ its reference to the shrine of Li Longqian on Ox Heart Hill, his efficacy, as well as the court-ordered repairs on the hill's rift in 824 provides independent evidence that corroborates the religious significance of both Li and the hill described by Du Guangting in the *DLJ*.

There is an additional complexity surrounding the *YQ* itself that warrants brief discussion. Scholars have noted considerable discrepancies between the present version of the *YQ*, found in the Ming Daoist Canon, and Zhang Junfang's description of the *YQ* in his original preface to the compendium. Of particular relevance to my discussion in this paper is the fact that while Zhang's preface states that the *YQ* comprised 120 *juan*,¹⁸ the present version consists of 122 *juan*. Of the thirty-seven tales missing from the *DZ* edition of the *DLJ*, thirty are found in the

¹⁶ For example, the eunuch Shang Shiqian comes up both *Jiu Tang shu* and the *DLJ*, but *Jiu Tang shu* also mentions Duan Zhao and Li Jiang. *Jiu Tang shu*, however, makes no mention of Wang Yuanyou or Yuchi Rui, whom the *DLJ* says were also in charge of the repairs. Likewise, *Zizhi tongjian* mentions Yuchi Rui, who also appears in the *DLJ* account, but not the other persons.

¹⁷ Jin Yufu, *Zhongguo shixueshi*, 131, 140–42. Huang Yongnian, '*Jiu Tang shu*' *yu* '*Xin Tang shu*', 25, 29.

¹⁸ *YQ*, i–ii (“Preface”).

last two *juan* of the *YQ* (i.e., *juan* 121 and 122), and this may cast some doubt on the authenticity of these tales. Franciscus Verellen concedes that at present it is impossible to explain the discrepancies between Zhang's preface and the present version of the *YQ*, but he notes that "several *juan* [in the present *DZ* edition of the *YQ*] are divided into two parts—A (*shang* 上) and B (*xia* 下)—for no apparent reason, which further increases the total count of *juan* [in the present edition]."¹⁹ In other words, it must be acknowledged that the present version of the *YQ*, as preserved in the Ming Daoist Canon, has evidently undergone changes. The arrangement into *juan*, for instance, is noticeably different, and there is no satisfactory explanation for this. However, no evidence suggests that the last two *juan* of the *YQ* in the Ming Daoist Canon are forgeries or later additions.

The present study uses a modern edition of *DLJ*, published in 2013 with editorial notes and interpuncts. This edition was based on the *DZ* edition with missing tales added from the *DZ* version of *YQ*.

¹⁹ Schipper and Verellen, *The Taoist Canon: A Historical Companion to the Daozang*, 944.

APPENDIX 2. TRANSLATIONS OF KEY SOURCE MATERIALS IN CHRONOLOGICAL ORDER

2.1 “Evidence from Li Shang Felling Pines and Cypresses in the Ancient Abbey on Ox Heart Hill in Longzhou” 李賞斫龍州牛心山古觀松栢驗, by Du Guangting (c. 905–908)

The ancient abbey on Ox Heart Hill in Longzhou was dedicated to Li Longqian, the distant ancestor of the Great Tang. When Xiao Ji (508–553), Prince Wuling of the Liang dynasty (502–557), governed the Yi region, he had Li Longqian build a fortress at this location. After his passing, Li was buried on the side of the hill. Local people erected a shrine for him, known as the “Shrine to Li the Ancient.” During the Wude reign (618–626), it was converted into a [Daoist] abbey (*guan* 觀).

Later, Wu [Zetian] (r. 690–705) usurped the throne, secretly seeking to change the [heaven’s] mandate. She decreed that the veins of the hill (*shanmai*)²⁰ be severed. At the location where the ridge of the hill was dug through, the color of the water turned red, and its odor resembled that of blood. “At the end of the Tianbao era (742–756), the Brilliant August (i.e., Emperor Xuanzong, r. 712–756) sought refuge in Shu [in midst of the An Lushan Rebellion (755–763)] and entered the Swordgate Pass. An elderly man named Su Tan greeted the imperial carriage and presented a petition: “Ox Heart Hill in Longzhou is the dynasty’s ancestral tomb. This prefecture also derived its name from Li the Ancient.²¹ According to what has been passed down through generations, [the hill and Li the Ancient] both have numinous power to respond. The calamity that has befallen Your Majesty today is entirely caused by the digging ordered by Wu Zetian. I propose that Your Majesty provide a set of imperial garments, bury them at the point where the hill ridge was severed, repair the ridge and restore it to its original state. The hill will surely make a sound. In this way, the twin capitals [i.e., Chang’an and Luoyang] will soon be recaptured, and Your Majesty will soon be able to return to the palace.” The Brilliant August, finding his words extraordinary, immediately had a palace envoy²² take a set of imperial garments and state insignia, make offerings to the hill, and carry out the repairs. In accordance

²⁰ Whiteman, *Where Dragon Veins Meet*, 59–78.

²¹ The name of the prefecture (Longzhou) and Li Longqian share the same character, “long” 龍 (dragon).

²² I render both *neishi* 內使 and *zhongshi* 中使 as “palace envoys” in this text. Both terms refer to eunuchs. Charles O. Hucker translated *zhongshi* as “imperial commissioners.”

with the imperial decree, Prefect Su Miao exempted the local residents within proximity to the hill from paying next year's taxes and had them join efforts to fill and restore the ridge to its original conditions. The hill indeed made a sound akin to the lowing of a bull.²³ The following year, An Lushan was slain, and the imperial palace was recaptured. In the second year of Zhide, on the twenty-eighth day of the tenth month [December 13, 757], an imperial decree was issued, stating: "Within the borders of the former commandery of Jiangyou,²⁴ there stands a numinous hill. Since His Majesty went on a tour to Ba and Liang [i.e., Xuanzong's flight to Sichuan], it has repeatedly manifested its ability to resonate and respond. With deep affection for this prefecture, it is fitting to give it additional honors. May the status of Longzhou be elevated to that of a regional military command. May it be granted the title of the 'Commandery of Numinous Response.'"

In the fourth year of Changqing [824], palace envoys Zhang Shiqian,²⁵ Wang Yuanyou,²⁶ and Prefect Yuchi Rui²⁷ made repairs. In the third month of the inaugural year of Baoli [825], the palace envoy Yan Wenqing, on an imperial decree, again offered a *jiao* and made prayers. During the reign of Emperor Xizong (r. 873–888), the imperial clansman Li Teli submitted a memorial citing the previous events, requesting the renovation of the abbey and shrine and a

²³ The lowing of a bull and the severed hill ridge might have been explanations for seismic activities, for which this area experienced many in history, including a highly destructive 8.0 M_s earthquake on May 12, 2008. In the Tang, an earthquake was recorded for this area in 638, but there are numerous others recorded for the Chengdu Plain which may have affected this area. Wang Huian and Wen Liming, *Zhongguo dizhen lishi ziliao huibian*, vol. 1, 76. I am grateful to Anna Shields for suggesting this possible reading.

²⁴ Longzhou was intermittently known as "Jiangyou Commandery" 江油郡 in the sixth and early seventh centuries. The Tang adopted the name Longzhou in 627 but changed it to Jiangyou Commandery in 742. In 756 it was renamed Yingling Commandery, only to be changed back to Longzhou two years later. Throughout this period, Jiangyou was also the name of the county where the seat of Longzhou was located. Yue Shi, *Taiping huanyu ji*, 84.1681; Ouyang Xiu and Song Qi, *Xin Tang shu*, 42.1090.

²⁵ Zhang Shiqian was a eunuch serving in Sichuan in the 820s. He was an army-supervising administrative assistant (*jianjun panguan* 監軍判官) in 827 and a junior army-supervising commissioner (*jianjun xiaoshi* 監軍小使) in 829. Wang Qinruo 王欽若, *Cefu yuangui* 冊府元龜, 980.11516b; Liu Xu, *Jiu Tang shu*, 163.4264.

²⁶ Wang was a high-ranking eunuch. He was a Palace Secretary (*nei shumi shi* 內樞密使) and Administrator of Palace Attendants (*zhi neishi sheng shi* 知內侍省事) and then appointed Palace Commandant-protector of the Right Army of Inspired Strategy (*you shence jun hujun zhongwei* 右神策軍護軍中尉) and concurrently Commissioner of Merit and Virtue (Supervising Religious Establishments Situated along) the Avenues of the Right Section of the Capital (*youjie gongde shi* 右街功德使). *Quan Tang wen*, 750.7769a.

²⁷ I read Weichi Rui 蔚遲銳 in the original text as a scribal error for Yuchi Rui 尉遲銳. Yuchi Rui was Prefect of Longzhou in 824 and appointed Prefect of Hanzhou 漢州 (modern Sichuan) in the early ninth century. Sima Guang, *Zizhi tongjian*, 243.7838; Li Fang, *Wenyuan yinghua*, 410.2080a. The name "Weichi Rui" does not appear in other historical sources.

Golden Register Retreat. Thereupon Teli was appointed as the administrative supervisor of Longzhou. Together with Wang Yanzhong, a palace envoy of high rank, he went to the hill and carried out renovations. The court also instructed Yang Shili, military commissioner of Eastern Chuan,²⁸ to hire Yuan Daochang and other eminent Daoist priests and have them perform the Yellow Register Retreat, make a *jiao* offering to the hill, and pray for blessings. The hill also made a sound resembling the lowing of a bull. The following year, Huang Chao was slayed, and the capital was recaptured. Its numinous responses were just as they had been. In the third year of Zhonghe [883], a decree was issued to elevate the status of Jiangyou county to “renowned.”²⁹

Afterwards, Li Shang, a construction officer in Eastern Chuan, passed by the hill and the abbey. He noticed that the ancient pines and cypresses there could be used as construction materials. As he was building a public office and intending to claim credit for the accomplishment, Li went straight to the forest for logging without approval from the commissioner’s office. The hill was by the riverside, making transportation convenient. However, when the felled timber was not yet halfway transported, day and night, there were constant reprimands from divine beings (*shenren*). Li Shang vividly heard the voices of reprimand but did not know the way to appease or offer apologies. Eventually, his corrupt practices were exposed, and he became the target of public anger. The Lord of Langya, who is presently Minister of State (*xiangguo*),³⁰ had him executed in the market.”

[DLJ, 17.333–334; YQ, 122.2684–85]

龍州牛心山古觀即大唐遠祖隴西李龍遷，梁武陵王蕭紀理益州，使遷築城於此，所居既沒，葬於山側，鄉里立祠，號李古人廟。武德中改為觀。

²⁸ Eastern Chuan was a Tang province located in the northern part of modern Sichuan. I follow Richard L. Davis in translating it as “Eastern Chuan.” See Ouyang Xiu, *Historical Records of the Five Dynasties*, 60.

²⁹ For a classification of Tang counties, see Xiong, *Historical Dictionary of Medieval China*, 682.

³⁰ “Langya” could be a choronym (*junwang* 郡望) or part of a noble title, and the term “*xiangguo*” (Minister of State) is used here most likely as a general reference to someone who holds a nominal office of the highest ranks in the central government. Given these ambiguities, it is nearly impossible to determine whom “Lord of Langya” refers to. It is probably a reference to one of Wang Jian’s 王建 (847–918) foster sons who served as military commissioners of Eastern Chuan in the late ninth and early tenth centuries and subsequently received a nominal appointment to the highest ranks in government, i.e., Wang Zongdi 王宗滌 (d. 902), Wang Zongyu 王宗裕 (d. 901), and Wang Zongji 王宗佺 (d. 908). On their appointments to Eastern Chuan, see Yu Xianhao, *Tang cishi kao quanbian*, 3036–37. Wang Jian’s foster sons used “Langya” (as opposed to, for instance, “Taiyuan” 太原) as their choronym. For examples, see the inscription on Wang Zongkan’s 王宗侃 (858–923) epitaph cover and the reference to Wang Zongyu (“Prince Tong” 通王) in his daughter-in-law’s epitaph. See Liu Yumao and Rong Yuanda, *Chengdu chutu lidai muming quanwen tulu zongshi*, 51–53, and 37–38.

其後武氏篡國，潛欲革命，敕鑿斷山脉，其崗斷處，水色變赤，其腥如血。天寶末明皇幸蜀，駕入劔門，有老人蘇坦迎駕，奏曰：「龍州牛心山，國之祖墓，因李古人名，遂為州名，古老相傳，皆有靈應。陛下今日蒙塵之禍，乃則天掘鑿所致。請御衣一襲，藏於山脉斷處，修築復舊。山必有聲，如此則克復兩京，回鑾有日矣。」明皇異其言，即命內使齎御衣國信，祭山修築。刺史蘇邈准詔，以近山四鄉百姓放明年租稅，併功修〔墳〕〔墳〕，還使如舊。山果有聲如牛响焉。明年誅祿山，復宮闕。至德二年十月二十八日詔曰：「江油舊壤，境帶靈山。自狩巴梁，屢昭感應。眷茲郡邑，合有增崇。可昇龍州為都督府，賜號應靈郡。」

長慶四年中使張士謙、王元宥、刺史蔚遲銳修之。寶曆元年三月內使閻文清又齎詔祈醮。僖宗朝，宗子李特立復以前事上奏，請修觀及廟，置金籙道場。乃授特立龍州錄事參軍，與內使高品王彥忠就山修飾，委東川節度使楊師立選高法道士袁道常等開黃籙道場，醮山祈福，山亦有牛响之聲。明年誅黃巢，復京邑，靈應復如初。中和三年詔昇江油為望縣。

其後東川修造將李賞嘗過山觀，見貞松古栢皆可材用。因修立廨署，苟圖其功，不奉使司指揮，徑往望林採伐。山臨江滸，便於運載，所斫材木，撻運未半，日夜常有神人詬責之。賞歷歷聞所詬之聲，莫知禳謝之路。既而以贓賄發露，為眾所怒。今相國瑯琊公斬之於都市。

2.2 Entry on the Li Longqian Shrine in *Taiping huanyu ji*

Li Longqian Shrine: On a hill close to the city wall stands the Shrine to Li Longqian. When Emperor Xuanzong of the Tang dynasty sought refuge in Shu, he commanded the expansion and renovation of the shrine and had prayers offered. In the fourth year of Changqing [824], Emperor Jingzong (r. 824–827) dispatched Zhang Shiqian, [a eunuch] of high rank, to the site to investigate historical facts.

[Li Fang, *Taiping huanyu ji*, 84.1683]

李龍遷祠。左近郭山上有李龍遷祠，唐元宗幸蜀時，嘗令增修禱祝。至長慶四年，敬宗差高品張士謙至彼處尋訪事跡。

2.3 Entry on the Li Longqian Temple in *Fangyu shenglan*

Li Longxian [Longqian] Temple: According to *Records of Evidential Miracles in Support of Daoism (Daojiao lingyan ji)*, Li Hu was buried on Ox Heart Hill in Longchuan (i.e., Longzhou). Additionally, according to the “Record of Marvels of Ox Heart Hill” (*Niuxin shan lingyi ji*), when Xiao Ji, Prince Wuling of the Liang dynasty, governed the Yi region, he had Li Longqian build a fortress on Ox Heart Hill. After his passing, Li was buried on the side of the hill. Local people erected a shrine for him, known as the “Shrine to Li the Ancient.” During the Wude reign (618–626), it was converted into a [Daoist] abbey. Later, Wu [Zetian] (r. 690–705) changed the d0[heaven’s] mandate and had the veins of the hill severed. When the Brilliant August (i.e., Emperor Xuanzong) was visiting Shu, an elderly man named Su Tan presented a petition: “Ox Heart Hill in Longzhou is the dynasty’s ancestral tomb. The calamity that has befallen [Your Majesty] today is entirely caused by the digging ordered by Wu Zetian.” The Brilliant August thereupon ordered Prefect Su Miao to make repairs and fill and restore [the ridge] to its original conditions. The following year, An Lushan was slayed, and the imperial palace was recaptured. In the second year of Zhide [757], the status of Longzhou was elevated to that of a regional military command, and it was granted the title of the ‘Commandery of Numinous Response.’ When Emperor Xizong sought refuge in Shu [in flight from the Huang Chao rebels], the imperial clansman Li Teli³¹ requested that Daoist priests be dispatched to make a *jiao* offering to the hill and pray for blessings. The next year, the twin capitals were recaptured. It can be inferred from these two accounts that Li Hu and Longxian were the same person. Additionally, according to the annals of Emperor Gaozu (r. 618–626) in the *Book of the Tang*, Gaozu’s seventh-generation ancestor, named [Li] Gao, was King Zhaowu of the Liang† dynasty (400–421).³² Gao gave birth to Xin, Xin gave birth to Chong’er, Chong’er gave birth to Tianxi, Tianxi gave birth to Hu, Hu gave birth to Bing, Bing gave birth to Yuan. Yuan was the name of the Tang emperor Gaozu. His descendants include Xun, Zhong’er, Xi, Tianxi, Hu, Bing, Yuan, and Tang Gaozu. Under the Western Wei (535–557), [the Li family] was given the [Xianbei]

³¹ The second character in the given name (*li 立*) is missing in the original text. The imperial clansman Li Teli was also mentioned in two other texts by Du Guangting. See *DLJ*, 2.171 and Du Guangting, *Lidai chongdaoji*, 370.

³² This refers to the Western Liang† 西凉 dynasty (400–421) that ruled northwest China in the Sixteen Kingdoms Period. The dagger, as a typographical mark, is used here to distinguish it from the Liang (502–557) in the Southern Dynasties, which is referred to in other parts of this paper,

surname of Daye. Thus, Li Hu served in the Western Wei and not in the Liang [of the Southern Dynasties].

[Zhu Mu, *Fangyu shenglan*, 70.1231]

李龍仙廟 按《道教靈驗記》：李虎葬龍川之牛心山。又《牛心山靈異記》：梁武陵王紀理益州，使龍遷築城於牛心山。龍遷既沒，即葬於山側，鄉里立祠，號李古人廟。武德中改為觀。其後武氏革命，鑿斷山脈。明皇幸蜀，有老人蘇坦奏曰：「龍州牛心山，國之祖壠，今日蒙塵之禍乃則天掘鑿所致。」明皇即命刺史蘇邈併工脩填如舊。至德二年乃升龍州為都督府，號靈應郡。僖宗幸蜀，宗子李特請遣道士醮山祈福，明年遂復兩京。以二記考之則李虎與龍仙即一人也。又按《唐書·高祖紀》，七世祖曰暹，為（梁）〔涼〕昭武王，生歆，歆生重耳，重耳生熙，熙生天錫，天錫生虎，虎生昞，昞生淵，是為唐高祖。當西魏時賜姓大野氏。是虎祇仕西魏，亦非仕梁也。

2.4 “Inscription for the Shrine to Li Longqian” 李龍遷祠記, by Chang Baixiang, dated 1171

Upon his arrival in Longyang (i.e., Longzhou), Lord Shi of Meishan³³ (modern Sichuan) dreamed of a [Daoist] perfected man (*zhenren*), astride a black ox, approached the gate seeking an audience. His attire was magnificent, and his gaze penetrating. Lord Shi asked, “From where do you come?” “From the southwest,” he replied. “Where is your home?” “In the central peak.” After some while, the perfected man departed. At dawn [*sic*], he informed Shi, “The August Song is destined for a revival, and it will be supported and acclaimed by all under Heaven. Your Excellency should aspire to this vision.” Lord Shi in his dream understood its meaning with perfect clarity. The next morning, upon awakening, he told his attendants, “This must have been the Blessing-Conferring Marquis.” He rose early, ascended [Ox Heart] Hill in a carriage, and

³³ Lord Shi’s name was Shi Qi 史祁. The inscription on a stele dating from 1170 shows that Shi Qi was Prefect of Longzhou at the time. The stele, featuring a portrait of the God of Perfect Martiality (*Zhenwu* 真武), copied from a wall painting inside a Daoist abbey in Jiangxi, was placed inside the Jade Voidness Abbey (*Yuxu guan* 玉虛觀) in Longzhou. The actual location of the Jade Voidness Abbey in Song times cannot be determined, and no evidence indicates a connection between this abbey and the shrine to Li Longqian in the Song. As of my field trip in 2019, the stele is placed inside Bao’en Monastery 報恩寺, built in the fifteenth and located in the present-day seat of Pingwu county. A rubbing of the stele, mistakenly dated to 1120, is in the collection of Princeton University Art Museum (<https://static.artmuseum.princeton.edu/mirador3/?manifest=https://data.artmuseum.princeton.edu/iiif/objects/57552&canvas=https://data.artmuseum.princeton.edu/iiif/objects/57552/canvas/57552-canvas-62587>).

made offerings at the shrine. Seeing that Ox Heart Hill was [a small mound] standing alone and surrounded by myriad mountains, he was suddenly enlightened. He chuckled and said, “This is what he called the ‘central peak,’ isn’t it?” Subsequently, he cleared the thickets and leveled [the ground] on the peak, dismantled the old structures, and constructed a grand new palace, Therefore, clearing away the dense forest, leveling the peaks, dismantling the old structures, and constructing a grand new palace, with layered towers and mansions soaring majestically into [the sky of] purple clarity. By this means he demonstrated his piety, settle the divine being into his place, and accumulate blessings for the dynasty. Lord Shi commanded his subordinate, Chang Baixiang, a native of Jiayang (i.e., Jiazhou 嘉州, modern Sichuan) to narrate, in sequence and full scope, the numinous marvels (*lingyi*) of the Blessing-Confering Divine Lord, so as to caution those in the present age and illuminate [future generations] for eternity. How can I refuse?³⁴

Respectfully I write: The Blessing-Confering Marquis of Eternal Aid (*Chuixiu yongji hou*) in the Temple of Manifest Aid (*Xianji miao*) has a given name of Longqian and a family name of Li. He was from Chengji in Longxi [commandery].³⁵ From the Divine Lord, [one can trace a lineage connecting to] the Emperor of the Mysterious and Primordial (i.e., the deified Laozi),³⁶ who, by means of the Great Way, was a teacher and exemplar for ten thousand generations;³⁷ descending from the Divine Lord, there was Emperor Taizong of the Tang dynasty, who, by means of divine martial prowess, pacified the realm. Therefore, it is known that the Li clan produces sagacious persons throughout the generations.

In the final years of the Liang dynasty, the Divine Lord, born to a prominent family in Longyang, took this commandery and submitted himself to the Laing. His pure loyalty and great

³⁴ I read *qi wen yi ci* 其文以辭 as an error for *qi ke yi ci* 其可以辭.

³⁵ The Tang ruling house claimed to have hailed from Chengji in Longxi. See, for example, an epitaph of Gaozu’s daughter in Zhou Shaoliang and Zhao Chao, *Tangdai muzhi huibian xuji*, 201 (咸亨 023: 大唐房陵大長公主墓誌銘并序). Ouyang Xiu and Song Qi, *Xin Tang shu*, 1.1.

³⁶ The Tang emperor Xuanzong granted the title of “Great Sagely Emperor of the Mysterious and Primordial” (*Dasheng xuanyuan huangdi* 大聖玄元皇帝) to the deified Laozi in 743. See Xiong, “Ritual Innovations and Taoism under Tang Xuanzong.”

³⁷ This phrase, “teacher and exemplar for ten thousand generations” (*wanshi shibiao* 萬世師表) was usually used as an extolment of Confucius. Its first use, based on a search in Chinese Classic Ancient Books Database (*Zhongguo jiben guji ku* 中國基本古籍庫), was in Yu Jing’s 余靖 (1000–1064) inscription for the prefectural school of Hongzhou 洪州 (modern Jiangxi), composed in 1036. Yu Jing, *Wuxi ji*, 6.2b (洪州新置州學記).

righteousness filled the universe. When Xiao Ji, Prince of Wuling, was stationed in Shu, he recognized that Longyang was on the shortcut taken by Deng Ai (195–264) on his westward expedition to conquer Shu. Consequently, he had the Divine Lord build a fortress here to defend and protect the region of Chuan-Shu (i.e., Sichuan). Thereby, he rendered distinguished services to the people.³⁸ After his passing, he was buried at the foot of the hill, and the local people worshipped him in a shrine, calling it the “Shrine to Li the Ancient.” Whenever prayers were offered, his responses were like echoes [to a sound].

Emperor Taizong and his father, rising from their base in Jinyang (modern Taiyuan), marched directly into Chang’an and their orders went out to the entire realm. Therefore, during the Wude reign (618–626), the shrine was converted to a [Daoist] abbey and sacrificial ceremonies were conducted with great solemnity. When Wu Zetian assumed imperial authority, she clandestinely plotted a change in the heaven’s mandate. Hateful of the auspicious topography of the dragon hill,³⁹ she ordered the digging and severance of its western ridge. Where the ridge was severed, a spring gushed out, and the water turned into blood. The elderly shed tears and lamented, “Calamity will arise from this!”

During the An Lushan Rebellion, the Brilliant August (i.e., Emperor Xuanzong) fled westward to the Swordgate [Pass]. The Divine Lord, transforming into a presented scholar named Su Tan, greeted the imperial carriage and paid his respects. He addressed the emperor, saying, “The temple at Ox Heart Hill in Longzhou is [dedicated to] a distant ancestor of Your Majesty. From his name the prefecture derived its own, and people universally believe that he possesses numinous powers. The calamity that has befallen Your Majesty today is entirely caused by the digging ordered by Wu Zetian. I propose that imperial garments be buried at the location where the ridge was severed and that the ridge be filled with earth and repaired. [Once done,] the hill will surely make a sound. In this way, the twin capitals will be recaptured, and the imperial carriage will soon be able to return.” The Brilliant August marveled at his proposal. He had the palace envoy Li Wuzhi take a set of imperial garments and state insignia, make offerings to the hill, and carry out the repairs. Prefect Su Miao provided tax reliefs for local residents and had them join efforts to fill the gap and restore the ridge to its original conditions. The hill indeed

³⁸ Allusion to *Liji zhengyi*, 46.802b.

³⁹ The “dragon hill” (*Longshan*) apparently refers to Ox Heart Hill.

made a sound akin to the lowing of a bull. Shortly thereafter, An Lushan and Shi Siming were destroyed, and both capitals were recovered. All these achievements owed to the [Divine Lord's] subtle and unobtrusive (*youzan*) assistance, and consequently devotion to the deity was further intensified. In the second year of Zhide, on the twenty-eighth day of the tenth month [December 13, 757], an imperial decree was issued, stating: "In the land of the age-old district of Jiangyou, there stands a numinous hill. From the Liang to the Tang, we have received numerous blessings that are manifest. With deep affection for this dragon-land, it is ritually appropriate to glorify it with honors. May the status of Longzhou be elevated to that of a regional military command. May it be granted the title of the 'Commandery of Numinous Response.'"

In the eighth month of the second year of Changqing [824], Yuchi Rui, governor of this prefecture, submitted a memorial stating, "Ox Heart Hill is, for long, famous for its supernatural marvels (*shenyi*), but it has a rift caused by digging. Although the Brilliant August had it repaired, the restoration is not yet complete. I request additional work to fill it up. Emperor Jingzong approved the proposal and ordered a palace envoy, Zhang Shiqian, to mobilize ten thousand men for a comprehensive restoration. The full details of this event were later recorded in the *Comprehensive Mirror [for Aid in Government]*.

In the first year of Emperor Xizong's reign [873], the emperor once again dispatched a palace envoy, Yan Wenjing,⁴⁰ to make a *jiao* offering [to the hill]. It acted in accordance with its nature and gave a response.⁴¹ Early in the Guangming reign (880–881), Huang Chao caused turmoil within the passes [i.e., the capital region], and Xizong sought refuge in Shu. Thereupon the imperial clansman Li Teli⁴² submitted a memorial citing the previous events, requesting a renovation of the shrine and pressing for a Golden Register Retreat. Concurring fully, Xizong appointed Teli as the administrative supervisor of Longzhou and had him join the palace envoy Wang Yanzhong in diligently repairing the shrine buildings. Xizong further entrusted Yang Shili, military commissioner of Eastern Chuan, with the task of selecting Daoist priests, including Yuan Daochang, to make a *jiao* offering for supplication. The hill once again made a sound resembling the lowing of a bull. An imperial decree conferred upon the Divine Lord the title of

⁴⁰ The last character of the envoy's name was given in the *DLJ* as *qing* 清 instead of *jing* 靖.

⁴¹ On the meaning of *xianruo* 咸若, which I render as "acting according to its nature," see Han and Tang commentaries on the *Book of Documents*. *Shangshu zhengyi*, 8.114a.

⁴² I read *Chili* 持立 as an error for *Teli* 特立.

“King of Treasured Tranquility” (*Baoding wang*); this occurred on the seventeenth day of the second month in the first year of Zhonghe [March 20, 881].⁴³ After the Huang Chao rebels had been exterminated and peace restored in the capital region, an edict was issued to elevate Jiangyou to the status of a “renowned” county,⁴⁴ in honor of the deity’s contributions.

Afterwards, Li Shang, a deputy commander in Eastern Chuan, passed by the dragon hill and saw pines and cypresses touching the sky and suitable for construction. As he was in charge of extensive repairs on a public office building, he headed straight for the hill and logged the trees without any reservations. Since the hill faced the Fu River, he planned on bundling the logs into rafts and flowing them downstream when the river flooded. That evening, however, a deity rebuked him vehemently in a stern voice. Those who heard it trembled in awe, and nobody could appease it. Soon after, Li Shang fell into disgrace for his corruption and was executed in the market by the Lord of Langya. This incident thus demonstrated, once again, the reverence that must be accorded to the Divine Lord’s numinous powers (*ling*).

Since the establishment of the Song dynasty, people in the prefecture and the county venerated the Divine Lord as if he were present⁴⁵ and dared not to be remiss in their reverence. On the fifth day of the eighth month in the second year of Chongning [September 7, 1103], Prefect Lei Shouren dreamed of the Divine Lord saying: “Please provide eight hundred strings of cash, and I will repay with a million.” The following day, an imperial edict was issued, demanding a renovation to the shrines of famous mountains and mighty streams. The edict stated that [those deities] who had not yet received a noble title may all request it. Lei Shouren therefore submitted a petition [for the Divine Lord], and on the sixth day of the twelfth month [January 5, 1104], an imperial decree was issued bestowing upon his shrine the title of “Temple of Manifest Aid.”⁴⁶ The expenses incurred in the renovation and the harvest reaped were

⁴³ In the seventh month of the second year of Guangming [881], the era name was changed from Guangming to Zhonghe. Strictly speaking, the second month of that year was in the Guangming era, but it is not uncommon to use the new era name for the whole year. Liu Xu, *Jiu Tang shu*, j. 19B. The grant of this kingly title cannot be verified in official historical sources.

⁴⁴ I read *shengxian* 聖縣 as an error for *wangxian* 望縣.

⁴⁵ I read this as an allusion to a sentence in The Analects (“He sacrificed to the dead, as if they were present. He sacrificed to the spirits, as if the spirits were present.” 祭如在，祭神如神在). *Lunyu zhushu*, 3.28a.

⁴⁶ The award of a plaque in 1104 can be verified by the entries in Xu Song, *Song huiyao jigao*, li 20.97. For a discussion of the meaning of “granting a plaque” (*ci’e* 賜額) in Song times, see Hansen, *Changing Gods in Medieval China*, 82.

precisely as the dream had predicted. In all instances, his numinous responses were clear and manifest, and [Lei's experience] was but one of such occurrences.

Subsequently, Cao Wu, the Left Martial Grand Master, Selected Elite Corps Commander with concurrent powers as Prefect of Fengzhou, made repairs to the lower hall,⁴⁷ and Tian Sheng, Governor of this prefecture and Commander-in-Chief of the Four Wings⁴⁸ of the Dragon and Inspired Guards, thereupon showed reverence and sought blessings. Guo Jiao, the Vice Prefect and Left Gentleman for Discussion,⁴⁹ recorded it in writing.⁵⁰ Guo also did the calligraphy for the plaque of the shrine.⁵¹ His brushwork flew into motion, exhibiting extraordinary grace that far surpassed the ordinary. In less than a decade, the building [of the lower hall] had fallen into disrepair. Today, Lord Shi of Meishan moved it in front of the main hall and had it repaired. The old plaque was then reinstated atop, turning it into a [hall-style] entrance gate.

From the Liang to the Tang and through to the August Song, nearly seven hundred years have passed. The blessings bestowed by the deity upon the people have extended ever farther and become more profound, and this has received commendation from the court. In the twenty-sixth year of Shaoxing [1156], the deity was granted the title of the Blessing-Confering Marquis of Eternal Aid.⁵² This is to make his virtue manifest through a thousand years and proclaim his grand announcements for eternity.

At first, Lord Shi of Meishan dreamed again of a bull with a yellow talisman covering its face. Neither its head nor horns were visible. The next day, an imperial decree was issued on

⁴⁷ The character *cai* 纒 in Cao's title is likely a scribal error. Cao Wu once served in Wu Jie's 吳玠 (1093–1139) army, stationed on the Sichuan-Shaanxi border, as a low-ranking officer. *QSW*, 294:6696.152.

⁴⁸ I read *simiao* 四廟 as an error for *sixiang* 四廂. I read *cishi* 刺史 as an alternate name for *zhizhou* 知州, not as a titular office.

⁴⁹ I read 佐承議郎 as an error for 左承議郎 (rank 7b). Usually *biejia* 別駕 was an old-Tang style prestige title (*sanguan* 散官) and translated as an “administrative aide” (rank 9a). In this context, I read it as an alternate name for *tongpan* 通判 (i.e., vice prefect, rank 7b if it was in a prefecture categorized as “small” [*xiazhou* 下州], such as Longzhou).

⁵⁰ In 1165, Tian Sheng was Prefect of Longzhou and Guo Jiao the Vice Prefect. *QSW*, 224:4962.19.

⁵¹ The meaning of *an'e* 案額 is unclear and may contain scribal errors. Judging from the context, I read it as *miao'e* 廟額 or *bang'e* 榜額, referring to the wooden plaque with the shrine's name and hung above the entrance of the temple or one of its halls. Alternatively, one may read it as an error for *zhuan'e* 篆額, referring to the seal-script heading on a stele.

⁵² This is at variance with *Song huiyao jigao*, which states that the god was awarded the title of Blessing-Confering Marquis in 1156 and was promoted to the “Blessing-Confering Marquis of Eternal Aid” in 1166. Xu Song, *Song huiyao jigao*, li 20.97.

yellow paper (*huangchi*) that appointed [Lord Shi's] successor. The talisman (*fu* 符) is [a pun for] the Military Commission (*anfu* 安撫).⁵³

Lord Shi of Meishan, seeing that the deity's date of birth was not known, personally prayed at the shrine. At night, he dreamed of the deity telling him, "I was born in the midnight hours on the second day of the fifth lunar month." Lord Shi kept his dream secret and gathered a large crowd of scholars and commoners at the shrine. Two divination sticks (*chou*) were prepared, one blank and the other containing a message. After burning incense, [Lord Shi] drew a stick, and the result turned out just as he had dreamed. Shortly afterward, the deity descended into the Shrine to the Brilliant August (*Minghuang miao*).⁵⁴ He possessed a person [i.e., spirit medium]⁵⁵ and [through that person] spoke, "I am the Blessing-Conferring [Marquis]. I was born to this world on the second day of the fifth month in the second year of the Tianjian era of Emperor Wu of Liang (r. 502–549) [June 11, 503]." This, once again, matched perfectly Lord Shi's dream like the two halves of a tally. Ah! Had it been not a deity of the greatest virtue, what else could accomplish these?

Taking orders from Lord Shi, I, [Chang] Baixiang, have diligently examined local gazetteers, explored ancient steles, formed a judgment based on *the Comprehensive Mirror [for Aid in Government]*, and composed this account. Now I compile the essentials and respectfully present them to Lord Shi: "The people are the deities, and the deities are the people; they are one and the same. Hence, the people are the master of the deities. 'Employ the people as if you were assisting at a great sacrifice.'⁵⁶ the reverence and solemnity [accorded to the people] is as such. To alienate the people is to alienate the deity; when the hearts of the people are in harmony, the

⁵³ I read *anfu* 安撫 as *anfusi* 安撫司. It might be an implicit reference to Shi Qi's next appointment, the current office of Shi's successor, or the office that made the appointment decision on Shi Qi, although the decision appear to have been approved and announced *pro forma* by the court on yellow paper (the yellow paper was reserved for imperial decrees).

⁵⁴ The Shrine to the Brilliant August apparently refers to a shrine dedicated to Tang Emperor Xuanzong. It is unclear whether the Shrine to the Brilliant August was located on Ox Heart Hill or in close proximity to the Shrine to Li Longqian in Shi Qi's times. Nor is it clear whether two shrines have a special religious connection in Song times. The earliest description of the Shrine to the Brilliant August is from a fifteenth-century national geography, which shows that the shrines to Xuanzong and Li Longqian were in two different locations. Chen Xun, *Huanyu tongzhi*, 70.3b.

⁵⁵ On reading *furen* as possessing a spirit medium, see Edward L. Davis, *Society and the Supernatural in Song China*, 100.

⁵⁶ Quote from *The Analects*, see *Lunyu zhushu*, 12.106ab.

intentions of the deity are fulfilled.” Delighted, Lord Shi said, “This is what I aspire after.” Then he proceeded to have these words inscribed [onto the stele].

Composed by Chang Baixiang, [Lord Shi’s] subordinate, Left Gentleman for Governmental Participation, dispatched directly from his previous office⁵⁷ to Longzhou as the Administrator of the Revenue and Law Sections, with a concurrent appointment as Instructor of the Prefectural School,⁵⁸ on the twenty-eighth day of the eleventh month in the seventh (*xinmao*) year of Qiandao [December 26, 1171]. Respectfully list: The Right Gentleman for Court Audiences, Prefect of Longzhou, Superintendent of Education, with concurrent responsibilities for Agricultural Development in his jurisdiction and as Chief Military Inspector of the borders of his jurisdiction, Lord Shi, whose name is Qi.⁵⁹ Respectfully appended.

[*QSW*, 242:5422.348–50]

眉山史公初莅龍陽，夢一真人跨青牛踵門求見，衣冠甚偉，目光射人。公問之曰：「奚自？」對曰：「自西南。」「家在何許？」曰：「中峰。」良久乃去。旦告公曰：「皇宋當中興，天下推戴，公其志之。」公夢中了然，識其所謂。晨起顧鈴下曰：「是必垂休侯也。」公夙駕登山，奠謁祠下，見牛心獨立不倚，萬山環之，忽悟，笑曰：「此所謂中峰者耶？」於是闢林莽，平峰巒，舊宇盡撤，新宮宏大，重樓複閣，凌厲紫清，所以揭虔妥靈、為國集福焉。公命其僚嘉陽常百祥叙次垂休神君靈異始末，以警動當世，昭示罔極，其文以辭。

謹按：顯濟廟垂休永濟侯諱龍遷，姓李氏，隴西成紀人也。自神君之上，則有元元皇帝，以大道為萬世師表；自神君而下，則有唐太宗以神武而定天下，因知李氏世生哲人矣。

⁵⁷ In Song times, officials usually traveled to the capital for reassignment after completing their tenure. Sometimes, however, without proceeding to the capital, some officials were directly dispatched to assume duties elsewhere. This practice was referred to as *jiuyi* 就移 or *jiuchai* 就差, which I render here as “dispatched on the spot” or “dispatched directly from his previous office.” For a brief discussion of *jiuchai*, see Deng Xiaonan, *Songdai wenguan xuanren zhidu zhu cengmian*, 201.

⁵⁸ The original text states that Chang concurrently managed the affairs of the Instructor of the Prefectural School in Fuzhou 涪州 (modern Chongqing). This is unlikely given the distance between Longzhou and Fuzhou (about 600 kilometers). I suspect that the text contains an error and that Chang served in the prefectural school of Longzhou.

⁵⁹ The meaning of *fengkai* is not entirely clear, and the simultaneous use of honorific (*gong* 公) and self-depreciatory phrases (*jin* 謹) at the end of this text is also unconventional. There may be scribal errors, and my translation is tentative.

當梁之末，神君龍陽大姓，舉郡以臣梁，精忠大義，充塞宇宙。及武陵王蕭紀鎮蜀，謂龍陽乃鄧艾征西取蜀捷徑，遂委神君築城於此，以捍蔽川蜀，有大功於民。既歿，葬山下，邦人祠之，號李古人廟。凡有禱者，其應如響。

太宗父子緣晉陽直入長安，號令天下，故武德中改廟曰觀，祭享甚嚴。則天稱制，潛謀革命，惡龍山之勝，遂鑿斷西岡。岡斷泉湧，水變成血，父老揮涕曰：「禍自此起矣。」

安史之亂，明皇西狩自劍門，神君化為進士蘇坦，迎鑾而拜，進言曰：「龍州牛心山廟，陛下遠祖也。因其名以為州名，人皆靈之。陛下今日蒙塵，乃則天鑿山之禍也。請藏御衣於鑿斷處，增土而築之，山必有聲，如是則兩京自復，翠華速歸矣。」明皇異之，遣中使李務直賫御衣國信祭山修築。刺史蘇邈蠲民租賦，竝力填之，復還舊物。山果發聲如牛响焉。未幾，殄安、史，復兩京，皆仗幽贊之功，益加欽奉。至德二年十月二十八日詔曰：「江油古邑，地帶靈山，自梁迄唐，屢蒙顯貺。眷茲龍境，禮合褒崇。可昇龍州為都督府，賜號靈應郡。」

長慶四年八月，本州刺史尉遲說上言：「牛心山素稱神異，有掘斷處，明皇修之而未盡，請加補塞。」敬宗從之，命中使張士謙役致萬人盡補之，而後以其事具載於《通鑑》。

至僖宗元年，復命中使閻文靖醮之，咸若有感。廣明初，黃巢亂關中，僖宗幸蜀，宗子持立具奏前事，請修廟及勸置金籙道場，僖宗深然之，即授持立本州錄事參軍，與中使王彥忠虔葺祠宇，委東川節度使楊師立選道士袁道常等設醮以禱之，山復有牛响之聲。勅封神君為寶定王。時中和元年二月十七日也。及巢賊滅，京邑再平，詔昇江油為聖縣，以旌神功。

其後東川副將李賞過龍山，見松柏參天，可為材用，大葺廡宇，遂發山刊木，絕無顧忌。山枕涪江，將束棧，乘江漲而下。其夕，有神訴責，其聲甚厲，聞者震駭，莫能禳也。俄而賞以賄敗，琅琊公戮之於市。則神君之靈，不可不敬者，又見於此也。

宋興以來，郡邑事神君如存，莫敢少懈。崇寧二年八月五日，刺史雷壽仁夢神君來告曰：「願得八百緡，當以百萬為報。」明日有詔修名山大川之祠，未封爵者皆上請。雷壽仁奏之，十二月六日勅賜顯濟廟為額。其修建之費，豐登之報，竟協於夢。凡靈應昭著，此其類也。

其後左武大夫、選鋒將纔領知鳳州曹武修下殿，本州刺史、龍神衛四（廟）〔廂〕都指揮使田晟相繼崇奉孚佑，州別駕（佐）〔左〕承議郎郭郊為文紀之，竝親書案額、筆勢飛動，有絕塵之姿。曾未十年，樓屋頽圯，今眉山史公遷之於正殿之前而鼎新之，仍置舊額於其上，為門樓焉。

自梁迄唐、至於皇宋幾七百年矣，神之澤民愈遠而益深，朝廷嘉之。紹興二十六年，封垂休永濟侯，所以發德於千載，揭大號於無窮也。

初，眉山史公再夢一牛黃符障面，不見頭角。翌日，黃勅下代者。符，安撫也。

公為神君無生日，親禱於廟，夜夢神君自言曰：「予伍月初二日子時生。」公秘之，令士民大會祠中，置籌二枚，空者一而言者二，炷香捻之，果如公夢。已而神降明皇廟中，附人而言曰：「我垂休也，誕降於梁武天監二年五月二日。」又與公夢若合符節。嗚呼，非盛德，其孰能焉！

百祥尊公之命，上考圖經，旁搜古碣，折中於《通鑑》以記之。綴其大者敬獻於公曰：「民則神，神則民，民神一也。故民者神之主，而使民如承大祭，其尊且嚴如是。苟失民則失神，民心合而神意得矣。」公忻然曰：「吾志也。」遂刊之。

門生左從政郎、就差龍州司戶參軍兼司法、管涪州學教授常百祥撰。時乾道七年歲次辛卯十一月二十八日，奉開右朝請郎、知龍州軍、主管學事、兼管內勸農事、兼管界沿邊都巡檢使、眉山史公諱祁。謹跋。

2.5 “Stele Inscription for Renovating the Branch Shrine to the Master of the Soil” 重修土主行祠記碑, by Wu Shiyu 吳士彧 (jinshi of 1415), dated 1424 (excerpts)

The Divine Lord, Master of the Soil of Longyang (i.e., Longzhou), was a descendant of Great Sagely Emperor of the Mysterious and Primordial (i.e., the deified Laozi) and a distant ancestor of the Tang ruling house. He hailed from Chengji in Shaanxi province, and his given name was Longqian. By nature, he was loyal (*zhong* 忠), upright, valiant, and upheld great righteousness. During the final years of Emperor Wu’s reign in the Liang dynasty, [Xiao] Ji (508–553), Prince of Wuling, governed this commandery. At that time, [the Divine Lord] cleared the brambles and thorns and built a fortress. A shepherd of his people, he led them to cultivate the fields and prepare for defense, thereby safeguarding the Shu region. When the Wei dynasty took control of Chang’an, it inspired awe throughout the realm, and all who heard of it were

filled with trepidation. However, the Divine Lord never lost the dutiful ethic of a ruler's servant and successfully defended this territory. Therefore, the people were able to live in peace, engaging in pleasure outings through four seasons, and the sounds of singing and dancing resonate continuously, up to the present day. Truly significant were the services that he rendered to the people!⁶⁰ Upon his passing, local people mourned and wailed for him. They erected a shrine on Ox Heart Hill [to venerate him] and built a branch shrine on Dragon Returning Mountain in the prefecture. [Such branch shrines exist] in various townships, numbering over a hundred. In times of drought, flood, and plagues, and when faced with doubts and uncertainties, they invariably turn to the shrine for prayer and supplication. When marauders invaded and caused harm to the people, the Divine Lord covertly assisted by giving commands to spectral troops (*yinbing*). As their drums resounded and flags unfurled,⁶¹ the marauders were immediately vanquished. From the Liang and Tang to the Song and Yuan dynasties, [the deity has] repeatedly [demonstrated his numinous powers]. He has “boldly and successfully met great calamities and warded off great evils.”⁶² The deity's achievements in various [generations] are fully recorded in stone inscriptions. Therefore, successive dynasties have revered and honored him, culminating in the bestowal of the title of “Manifestly Responsive, Loyal and Benevolent, and Broadly Protective King.” Additionally, his wife and sons have also been awarded the titles of Marquis and Consort....

[Xiang Yuanmu, *Pingwu wenwen daguan*, 199–200]

龍陽土主神君，大聖玄元皇帝之裔，李唐遠祖也，陝西成紀人，諱龍遷，天性忠直豪傑仗大義。當梁武末年，武（肅）〔陵〕王紀（余）〔來〕守是郡，時披荆壘築城郭，牧民禦泉且畊且守，而保障蜀川。逮魏據長安，威震天下，聞者莫不戰慄。神君終不失臣節，克守其地，以民安如堵，四時嬉遊，歌舞之聲相〔屬〕，至於今不〔絕〕。其有功於民也甚矣。既（設）〔沒〕，郡人思君號泣，立廟於牛心山，復修行祠於郡之龍歸山，而各鄉百有餘所，〔凡〕水旱疾疫決〔疑〕定豫，必叩廟求禱焉。或寇犯茲境，為民害，神君既麾陰兵默助，鳴鼓張旗，寇隨自（滅）〔滅〕。自梁〔唐〕迄宋元，屢〔昭感〕

⁶⁰ Allusion to *Liji zhengyi*, 46.1524.

⁶¹ Note that the phrase “*minggu zhangqi*” is precisely what was used in the thirteenth-century edict translated above.

⁶² Allusion to the *Book of Rites*, see *Liji zhengyi* 46.1524.

應〕。禦大災、捍大〔患〕，神功異〔〔世〕〕，〔〔具〕〕載碑碣，故歷代尊崇，加封至「顯應忠惠廣護王」。暨夫人、子悉封爵侯妃……⁶³

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Abbreviations

YQ Zhang Junfang, *Yunji qiqian*.

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⁶³ The transcription in *Pingwu wenwen daguan* includes many errors, which are corrected here based on the actual stele that I saw in Bao'en Monastery, Pingwu county, Sichuan during my field trip. Deletions and insertions are indicated with () and [] respectively.

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